

Online supplement to:

Left ventricle diastolic vortex ring characterization in ischemic cardiomyopathy: insight into atrio-ventricular interplay

**Alessandra Riva^{1,2}, Simone Saitta², Francesco Sturla^{1,2,*}, Giandomenico Disabato³,
Lara Tondi^{3,4}, Antonia Camporeale³, Daniel Giese⁵, Serenella Castelvechio⁶,
Lorenzo Menicanti⁶, Alberto Redaelli², Massimo Lombardi³, Emiliano Votta^{2,1}**

¹ 3D and Computer Simulation Laboratory, IRCCS, Policlinico San Donato, San Donato Milanese, Italy

² Department of Electronics, Information and Bioengineering, Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy

³ Multimodality Cardiac Imaging, IRCCS Policlinico San Donato, San Donato Milanese, Italy

⁴ Department of Radiology, IRCCS Foundation Ca' Granda Ospedale Maggiore Policlinico, University of Milan, Milan, Italy

⁵ Magnetic Resonance, Siemens Healthcare GmbH, Erlangen, Germany

⁶ Cardiac Surgery Department, IRCCS Policlinico San Donato, San Donato Milanese, Italy

**Corresponding author:*

Francesco Sturla

francesco.sturla@grupposandonato.it

IRCCS Policlinico San Donato

Piazza E. Malan 2

San Donato Milanese, Italy

LA analysis

LA volumes and strain by cardiac MRI are usually evaluated by applying the biplane area-length algorithm and the feature tracking method to standard long-axis 2- and 4-chamber cine bSSFP images (Kowallick *et al.*, 2014). Analysis of the LA included LA V^{\max} , LA V^{preA} , LA V^{\min} , LA EF and LA strain. The biplane area-length method was applied to estimate LA volumes using the following formula:

$$LA V = \frac{0.85 \cdot LA Area_{4chamber} \cdot LA Area_{2chamber}}{L_{min}} \quad \text{S.1}$$

where L_{min} was the shorter long-axis length of the LA either from the 2-chamber or the 4-chamber view.

LV analysis

The LV DSI was computed through the following formula:

$$LV DSI = \frac{LV EDV}{\frac{4}{3}\pi \left(\frac{LV long axis}{2}\right)^3} \quad \text{S.2}$$

where the LV long axis diameter is computed as the average between the measurements obtained from the 2-chamber and 4-chamber views (Castelvecchio *et al.*, 2018; Mannaerts *et al.*, 2004). LV EDV and LV long-axis are expressed in mm^3 and mm, respectively.

LVGFI is a global, structural and functional parameter that combines LV stroke volume, end-systolic and end-diastolic LV volumes and LV mass. It is computed using the following formula (Mewton *et al.*, 2013):

$$LVGFI = \frac{LV SV}{LV global volume} \cdot 100 \quad \text{S.3}$$

where LV global volume was defined as:

$$LV global volume = LV mean cavity + myocardial volume$$

$$LV mean cavity = \frac{LV EDV + LV ESV}{2} \quad \text{S.4}$$

$$myocardial volume = \frac{LV mass}{1.05}$$

Semi-automatic method for the choice of K

A semi-automatic method to set the value of K was implemented and it was based on an objective and repeatable criterion that could translate a qualitative and visual inspection into an objective identification of the vortex ring.

First, the parameter K should minimize the presence of trailing structures originating from the main vortex ring, and it was noticed that the smaller the value of K the more trailing structures remain (**Figure S3.a**). Second, the selected value of K should still yield a toroidal vortex ring core, as also described in previous studies exploiting the λ_2 method (Elbaz, Calkoen, *et al.*, 2014; Elbaz *et al.*, 2017; Elbaz, Lelieveldt, *et al.*, 2014). In this case, the higher the value of K , the more the core ring loses its toroidal shape (**Figure S3.c**). Therefore, an optimal trade-off value of K should exist, which is large enough to reduce, or ideally remove, trailing structures but is small enough to preserve the toroidal shape of the vortex ring (**Figure S3.b**).

The semi-automatic method is based on the quantification of the two trends, and it consists of four steps, that were performed both at peak E-wave and at peak A-wave, for each subject of the study population:

Step 1 – Automatic generation of vortex rings for multiple K values

Values of K ranging from 1 to 5 with a step of 0.1 are considered. For each value, the vortex region is identified as a binary mask, where a value of 1 is associated to voxels characterized by $\lambda_2 < K\mu$, and μ is the λ_2 average of voxels with $\lambda_2 < 0$. For each value of K , the number of trailing structures and the vortex circularity index (CI, see the following paragraph) were automatically quantified (*Steps 2 and 3*, respectively).

Step 2 – Quantification of the number of trailing structures

The skeleton of the 3D binary mask is created using the function Skeleton3D (Lee *et al.*, 1994), which reduces the mask to a one-voxel-wide representation. The network graph of the 3D voxel skeleton is then computed (Kollmannsberger *et al.*, 2017): for each point of the skeleton, the number of first-order neighbours is obtained, thus allowing to identify bifurcation-points, i.e., points where more than two tracts of the skeleton originate. Given the bifurcation points, the vortex skeleton is then subdivided into links, and the number of links (N) is a surrogate measure of the number of trailing structures (**Figure S4**).

The number of links vs. K relationship is exemplified for one healthy control and for one ICM patient in **Figure S5** (yellow line).

Step 3 – Quantification of the vortex CI

As the value of K is excessively increased, the vortex ring loses its torus-like shape; only a portion of the torus remains, and this is typically on one side of the original shape. Therefore, the remaining region has the shape of a curved cylinder, which has one predominant dimension. On this basis, CI is determined using principal component analysis (see the following paragraph), which allows for identifying the first two principal directions, corresponding to the long- and the short-axis of the vortex

ring, and CI is computed by their ratio. CI vs. K is exemplified for the same patient in **Figure S5** (blue line).

Step 4 – Selection of the optimal K value

The optimal K value should simultaneously yield low CI and N values. Hence, the optimal K value is within the range identified by the green interval in **Figure S5**.

Vortex ring analysis

The 3D spatial coordinates of the voxels belonging to the identified vortex region were extracted and stored in a matrix $\mathbf{X} = [x_1, \dots, x_n, \dots, x_N]$, with N being the total number of selected voxels and $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 3}$. Then, principal component analysis (PCA) was applied to \mathbf{X} . PCA projects the coordinates data onto a linear space of maximum variation directions, i.e., the principal components (Jolliffe & Cadima, 2016). PCA begins by computing the mean of the data distribution (in this case, the center of mass of the vortex):

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N x_n \tag{S.5}$$

and by assembling the covariance matrix \mathbf{C} , given by:

$$\mathbf{C} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (x_n - \bar{x})(x_n - \bar{x}^T) \tag{S.6}$$

Using singular value decomposition (SVD) on \mathbf{C} , PCA identifies the sequence of eigenvectors that progressively maximize the explained dataset variance. In our case, the largest eigenvector of \mathbf{C} , represents the straight line that best fits (in a least square sense) the 3D vortex points, forming an orthonormal basis with the second and third eigenvectors, identifying the short axis of the vortex ring and the direction normal to its best fit plane, respectively. For each of the first two eigenvectors, a set of points is generated and, among these, the two furthest points falling within the convex hull of the vortex points \mathbf{X} are identified: A and B for the first eigenvector (long axis, **Figure 1a**) and C and D for the second eigenvector (short axis, **Figure 1a**). Distances between A and B (D_1) and between C and D (D_2) define the vortex axis lengths, and the vortex circularity index (CI) is computed as their ratio.

Divergence impact on viscous dissipation

The divergence of flow velocity for incompressible flow must be ideally equal to zero. However, velocity measurements obtained through 4D Flow MRI contain errors, causing the divergence to typically deviate from zero (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). To address potential inaccuracies, we evaluated the effect of the divergence on the computation of the viscous dissipation as follows:

$$div \% = \frac{|\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}|}{\phi_v} \cdot 100 \quad \text{S.7}$$

where ϕ_v and $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}$ were computed as:

$$\phi_v = 2 \left[\left(\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v_z}{\partial z} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{3} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v})^2 \right] + \left(\frac{\partial v_y}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v_z}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial z} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial x} \right)^2 \quad \text{S.8}$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \quad \text{S.9}$$

div % was evaluated at the LV and at the VR levels, both at peak E-wave and at peak A-wave for the entire study population (**Figure S7**). *div* % for the LV ranged between 0.001% and 0.34% at peak E-wave and between 0.001% and 0.12% at peak A-wave. *div* % for the VR ranged between 0.003% and 0.38% at peak E-wave and between 0.02% and 0.21% at peak A-wave. Therefore, given the negligible impact of $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}$ on the overall ϕ_v , we kept its contribution to the total viscous dissipation.

References

- Castelvecchio, S., Careri, G., Ambrogi, F., Camporeale, A., Menicanti, L., Secchi, F., & Lombardi, M. (2018). Myocardial scar location as detected by cardiac magnetic resonance is associated with the outcome in heart failure patients undergoing surgical ventricular reconstruction. *European Journal of Cardio-Thoracic Surgery*, *53*(1), 143–149. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejcts/ezx197>
- Elbaz, M. S. M., Calkoen, E. E., Westenberg, J. J. M., Lelieveldt, B. P. F., Roest, A. A. W., & van der Geest, R. J. (2014). Vortex flow during early and late left ventricular filling in normal subjects: quantitative characterization using retrospectively-gated 4D flow cardiovascular magnetic resonance and three-dimensional vortex core analysis. *Journal of Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance*, *16*(1), 78. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12968-014-0078-9>
- Elbaz, M. S. M., Lelieveldt, B. P. F., Westenberg, J. J. M., & van der Geest, R. J. (2014). *Automatic Extraction of the 3D Left Ventricular Diastolic Transmitral Vortex Ring from 3D Whole-Heart Phase Contrast MRI Using Laplace-Beltrami Signatures* (pp. 204–211). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-54268-8_24
- Elbaz, M. S. M., van der Geest, R. J., Calkoen, E. E., de Roos, A., Lelieveldt, B. P. F., Roest, A. A. W., & Westenberg, J. J. M. (2017). Assessment of viscous energy loss and the association with three-dimensional vortex ring formation in left ventricular inflow: In vivo evaluation using four-dimensional flow MRI. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*, *77*(2), 794–805. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.26129>
- Jolliffe, I. T., & Cadima, J. (2016). Principal component analysis: a review and recent developments. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, *374*(2065), 20150202. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2015.0202>
- Kollmannsberger, P., Kerschnitzki, M., Repp, F., Wagermaier, W., Weinkamer, R., & Fratzl, P. (2017). The small world of osteocytes: connectomics of the lacuno-canalicular network in bone. *New Journal of Physics*, *19*(7), 073019. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1367-2630/aa764b>
- Kowallick, J. T., Kutty, S., Edelmann, F., Chiribiri, A., Villa, A., Steinmetz, M., Sohns, J. M., Staab, W., Bettencourt, N., Unterberg-Buchwald, C., Hasenfuß, G., Lotz, J., & Schuster, A. (2014). Quantification of left atrial strain and strain rate using Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance myocardial feature tracking: a feasibility study. *Journal of Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance*, *16*(1), 60. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12968-014-0060-6>
- Lee, T. C., Kashyap, R. L., & Chu, C. N. (1994). Building Skeleton Models via 3-D Medial Surface Axis Thinning Algorithms. *CVGIP: Graphical Models and Image Processing*, *56*(6), 462–478. <https://doi.org/10.1006/cgip.1994.1042>
- Mannaerts, H., van der Heide, J. A., Kamp, O., Stoel, M. G., Twisk, J., & Visser, C. A. (2004). Early identification of left ventricular remodelling after myocardial infarction, assessed by transthoracic 3D echocardiography. *European Heart Journal*, *25*(8), 680–687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ehj.2004.02.030>
- Mewton, N., Opdahl, A., Choi, E.-Y., Almeida, A. L. C., Kawel, N., Wu, C. O., Burke, G. L., Liu, S., Liu, K., Bluemke, D. A., & Lima, J. A. C. (2013). Left Ventricular Global Function Index by Magnetic Resonance Imaging—A Novel Marker for Assessment of Cardiac Performance for the Prediction of Cardiovascular Events. *Hypertension*, *61*(4), 770–778. <https://doi.org/10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.111.198028>
- Zhang, J., Brindise, M. C., Rothenberger, S., Schnell, S., Markl, M., Saloner, D., Rayz, V. L., & Vlachos, P. P. (2020). 4D Flow MRI Pressure Estimation Using Velocity Measurement-Error-Based Weighted Least-Squares. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, *39*(5), 1668–1680. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2019.2954697>

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. Left atrial function.

Figure S2. Definition of peak E-wave and peak A-wave timeframes, according to the kinetic energy (indexed to the LV volume) time course. The systolic phase is indicated as the grey area.

Figure S3. **a)** For low K values, the diastolic vortex ring has several attached trailing structures. **b)** The choice of the ideal K gives a torus(donut)-like shape. **c)** For high K values, large portions of the vortex ring (e.g., semi-transparent region) can be lost and the vortex ring loses its circular shape.

Figure S4. Schematic representation of a diastolic vortex ring with trailing structures attached. White circles represent the bifurcation points, while vortex skeleton is subdivided into links (coloured dashed lines).

Figure S5. CI-K (blue) and N-K (yellow) relationship for one healthy control (a) and for one ICM patient (b). The green interval represents the set of K values that would be suitable for the computation of the vortex ring. CI, circularity index; N, number of links in the skeleton of the vortex ring.

Figure S6. Exemplification of the possible shapes of the vortex ring.

Figure S7. Box and whiskers represent *div %*, evaluated at peak E-wave (a) and at peak A-wave (b) for the left ventricle and for the vortex ring. Each box ranges between 25th and 75th percentile, with a line pointing out the median value; whiskers indicate the minimum and maximum, respectively. LV, left ventricle; VR, vortex ring.

Figure S8. Top panel: Linear regression plots showing the Pearson correlation, from left to right, for α , CI and V_{VR} , for intra-operator analysis, with the fully manual approach. The plot shows the reference line (continuous line) and confidence interval at 95% (semi-transparent area). **Bottom panel:** Bland-Altman plots of the differences between Observer 1^a and Observer 1^b. CI, circularity index; SEE, standard error of estimate.

Figure S9. Top panel: Linear regression plots showing the Pearson correlation, from left to right, for α , CI and V_{VR} , for inter-observer analysis, with the fully manual approach. The plot shows the reference line (continuous line) and confidence interval at 95% (semi-transparent area). **Bottom panel:** Bland-Altman plots of the differences between Observer 1 and Observer 2. CI, circularity index; SEE, standard error of estimate.

Supplementary Tables**Table S1.** Diastolic function parameters obtained from 2D echocardiography at the time of MRI.

E/A	E/E'	Pulmonary arterial pressure [mmHg]
0.7 [0.63; 2.03]	9.8 ± 4.8	28 ± 5

Supplementary Video

Video S1. Temporal evolution of vortex ring 3D structures (represented in red) throughout diastole for one healthy control. **Left panel:** streamlines show blood flow direction and are displayed over a horizontal long-axis view. **Right panel, top:** short-axis view of the left ventricle. **Right panel, bottom:** temporal evolution of KE_{LV} throughout the cardiac cycle. The systolic phase is coloured in grey, while the current timeframe is highlighted through a red dot. KE, kinetic energy; S, systole.

Video S2. Temporal evolution of vortex ring 3D structures (represented in red) throughout diastole for one ICM patient. The ICM patient presents aneurysmal remodelling of the apex, with a thrombus adhered to the wall. **Left panel:** streamlines show blood flow direction and are displayed over a horizontal long-axis view. **Right panel, top:** short-axis view of the left ventricle. **Right panel, bottom:** temporal evolution of KE_{LV} throughout the cardiac cycle. The systolic phase is coloured in grey, while the current timeframe is highlighted through a red dot. KE, kinetic energy; S, systole.